

Research Proposal

for the PhD doctoral thesis of Lemenkova Polina at the
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Title: **Landscape Change in Tian Shan: Temporal Variation of Montane Ecoregions**

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WORK SCHEDULE: 3 years (March 2011 – March 2014)

RESEARCH AREA: *Tian Shan*, Mountains of Central Asia

RESEARCH PROBLEM:

The *Tian Shan*, or *Celestial Mountains*, is a large, isolated montane range, located in the border region of Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and western China (Xinjiang Uyghur Autonomous Region). *Tian Shan* is surrounded by the desert basins of northern China, extending 2,500 km east-to-west across Central Asia (Fig.1). Being the most northern montane range with more than 7.000 high peaks, *Tian Shan* possess unique and diverse montane environment, with more than 4000 wild species, many of which are endemic, rare and relict. The *Tian Shan* holds important forests of Schrenk's Spruce (Fig.2) at altitudes of over 2,000 metres; the lower slopes have unique natural forests of wild walnuts, wild fruits and apples. The most precious part of the unique biodiversity of *Tian Shan* are dense coniferous forests. They play an important role in the ecosystems of the *Tian Shan*, being hot spots of biodiversity rich in species and resources. Besides, they serve as a buffer belt against flooding and low-water runoff.

In the past decades the environment of the *Tian Shan* faced potential threats of both anthropogenic and natural origin, which can cause changes in the landscape structure of its very specific environment.

Thus, climate change mainly impacts glacier areas: ice sheet melting and general decrease of snow coverage in high mountains. Possible anthropogenic threats, that can induce landscape changes, include overgrazing at higher elevations by the local people, and local deforestation, which may lead to the

partial decrease in biodiversity of the *Tian Shan*. Finally, the work of forest management and guarding has been weakened in the last years. As a result of cattle overgrazing, fires, deforestation, terracing of slopes, assignment of the grounds under construction of various objects and other factors there is an essential reduction of an area of distribution of wood and tangled vegetation (Orozumbekov, 2010).

Due to the environmental threats and increased anthropogenic pressure on such fragile environment, if the present forestry policy continues, the forest area of the Tianshan mountains would decrease by 10-20% with 50 years (Baiping *et al*, 2004).

Another environmental challenge that *Tian Shan* ecosystems face nowadays is the retreat of glaciers.

According to the numerous reports of various researchers (Aizen, 2006; Bolch, 2007; Solomina *et al*, 2004; Kutuzov and

Fig.1. *Tian Shan*. Geographic location.

Source: <http://www.everest.org/tianshanindex.html>

Fig.2 Schrenk's Spruce forests in *Tian Shan*.

Source: <http://www.wikipedia.org>

Shahgedanova, 2009; Giese and Moßig, 2004; Narama *et al*, 2006; Niederer *et al*, 2007), in the last decades the *Tian Shan* glaciers suffer from the global climate warming on the planet and from overall increase of the temperatures. As a consequence, they reduce in their size drastically. Such alterations in *Tian Shan* glaciology inevitably lead to the changes its landscape structure and land cover patterns, which, in turn, trigger other, unstoppable processes in the environment. Thus, for example, melting of ice sheet in *Tian Shan*, causes flood hazards from montane rivers and glaciers (Jansky, 2010).

Therefore, up-to-date complex mapping of this unique region, which straddle three countries, is necessary for the monitoring of its environmental conditions and detecting any changes in the land cover types.

In the current work we plan to focus on two main thematic issues of the environmental changes in the *Tian Shan* ecosystems.

1. First, to monitor temporal dynamics of the glaciers distribution and their changes using remote sensing imagery, based on the spatial analysis of the satellite and aerial images using classification techniques. The temporal dynamics would cover time span of 30 years (since 1980) at least.
2. Secondly, to undertake spatial analysis of the land cover pattern structure in *Tian Shan*, as well as to detect, visualize and map any changes in the landscapes of the *Tian Shan* over the past 30 years.

We suggest to focus on 30-years period, because the industry of the satellite imagery started in early 1970-s, and the real development of the remote sensing techniques of Earth observation mostly starts from 1980s. However, if there are any older imagery or maps *Tian Shan* available (e.g. precise maps of *Tian Shan* glaciers or aerial images made in 1970s), they will be included in the work as well.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

The research aims to apply methods of spatial analysis based on open source GIS software (mostly, GRASS and GMT, also Idrisi for images classification). The main objective of the research is mapping the land cover types and quantitative estimation of their areas in *Tian Shan* region, with special attention towards coniferous forests areas (as the most precious part of the *Tian Shan* ecosystems). We also intend to investigate possible melting in glacier areas and losses in coniferous forests, and to do qualitative analysis of the impact of the environmental changes on the montane ecozones: biodiversity change detection.

The spatial analysis includes classification of the research area into different ecozones by means of the analysis of geomorphological and environmental conditions. Namely, at this working step we intend to incorporate various sources of data into the GIS project: use DEMs for geomorphological analysis, results of images classification with determined land cover types, plus vector map layers. The integration of data will enable us to investigate spatially single land cover patterns within the general structure of *Tian Shan*.

The temporal dynamics of the changes in glaciers will be based on the supervised classification and investigation of the ice distribution. The differences between the ice sheets on the images will be detected using various bands combinations on the masked images. The detected changes will be studied for the exact estimation of the changes in the ice areas.

Spatial analysis of the *Tian Shan* structure will help to highlight adaptation of different ecoregions of *Tian Shan* under conditions of high mountainous climate towards the changing environment: which regions undergone any changes and are, therefore, most environmentally vulnerable and have lesser resistance capability towards climate change. The detection of the ice sheet melting will display areas with the most rapid changes in the glacial structure of the *Tian Shan*.

TECHNICAL APPROACH

The spatial analysis of land cover patterns is suggested to be studied using images processing based on the available open sources: for example, satellite imagery from USGS (<http://www.usgs.gov/pubprod/>), The Earth Science Data Interface (<http://glcfapp.glc.f.umd.edu:8080/esdi/index.jsp>), GloVis (<http://glovis.usgs.gov/>), as well as aerial images (including those from famous Google Earth imagery), free DEMs (for example, from the open source <http://geomorphometry.org/content/data-sets> or any other) and vector maps. Any available other geodata sources will be considered during the research work.

The research data pool is suggested to be most up-to-date, covering period of approximately 10 years: since early 2000-s up to the latest time, depending on the availability.

The research is proposed to be technically based on *GRASS GIS* open source software as a major tool for spatial analysis and cartographic presentation; *Idrisi* software is going to be used for visualizing, processing and interpretation of geospatial imagery. Possibly, other software will be used during the working process as well. *GIS*-based spatial analysis is intended to detect any changes in montane ecozones, with special attention towards coniferous forests. The spatial analysis will be mainly based on the images classification (e.g. using supervised classification with training sites of coniferous trees) in order to investigate area distribution of various ecoregions within *Tian Shan* mountains.

The project is supposed to be based on the application of common principles of spatial modelling and GIS-mapping, as well as remote sensing techniques, applied to the case study of *Tian Shan* mountains.

EXPECTED RESULTS:

We suggest the final outcome of the proposed research work to include following cartographic results:

1. Small-scaled thematic analytical map showing actual general structure of *Tian Shan* mountains: its geomorphological sketch (3D visualisation using DEM), combined with thematic layers showing land cover types in *Tian Shan* nowadays. Thus, the cartographic outcome would be general 3D-map of the *Tian Shan* mountains representing overlay: geomorphology + landscape types of *Tian Shan*.
2. Map of the ice sheet and glacier changes, which should include various glaciers in different *Tian Shan* ranges and display the areas “before” and “after” intensive ice melting. We suggest to highlight the dynamic of changes covering time span of 30 years.
3. The zonal middle-scale maps of the spatial distribution of ecoregions over various areas of *Tian Shan* are planned to illustrate current situation in the structure of the *Tian Shan*. Here we plan to map three major geographic regions of *Tian Shan*: 1) *Eastern Tian Shan* in its Chinese part, 2) *Central Tian Shan* in Kyrgyzstan, incl. *Terskey Alatau* 3) *Fergana* - southern part of *Tian Shan*.
4. Visualisation of the selected areas of *Tian Shan* area in more detailed scale. The outcome should be several (three-five) large-scale maps. The areas of special interests, e.g. six National Parks of *Tian Shan*, biosphere reserves, etc. For example, *Chatkal National Park* and *Sary Chelek biosphere reserve* both included by UNESCO to the «Man and Biosphere program» due to their uniqueness (<http://www.unesco.org/new/en/natural-sciences/environment/ecological-sciences/man-and-biosphere-programme/>).

These areas we plan to investigate more detailly, depending on the available data and resources.

5. In case if there are any proved, detected changes in land cover types: statistical outcome estimating the

environmentally changed areas (for example, losses of forests areas, or changes of gletcher areas, if detected). If available, these results will include tables displaying calculations or areas.

SIGNIFICANCE

- 1) The proposed research work will be an important scientific contribution to the studies of the global montane biodiversity and nature conservation in high mountains.
- 2) Technically, we will apply various methods and tools of the open source GIS, and thus, explore the possibilities and limitations of the GRASS GIS towards landscape mapping and spatial analysis.
- 3) The suggested methodology of the spatial analysis and mapping of the landscapes of the *Tian Shan* mountains can be applied towards other montane areas with similar landscape structure.

KEYWORDS:

Tian Shan mountains, coniferous forests, ecoregions, environmental changes, spatial analysis, GRASS GIS, Idrisi, images classification, land cover types, geomorphological structure.

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